

ORGANIZING GENERAL STAGES OF INTENSIVE READING SKILL

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Annotation. In the article, the author shares experience with leveled reading books, which she applies as intensive reading in class, especially at the initial stage of higher education. The right choice of level helps students overcome psychological barriers in mastering a foreign language.

Key words: “passive” work of reading, arguments, “active” work, the topic of the passage, reflection.

Intensive reading is reading with full comprehension of the text. Reading is one of the most effective ways to improve language skills and perhaps the most enjoyable. So what techniques can be applied to maximize the use of IF? They are varied and depend on both the book itself and the students. They can be used regardless of the difficulty level of the book. Intensive reading works well in the tasks of improving pronunciation and listening if it is a read-aloud. Reading aloud, students tune in to the sound series of the target language. It is important, firstly, to work on pronunciation, otherwise the wrong “guessed” pronunciation of this or that word can annoy for years later. Secondly, it is possible to “dramatize” reading aloud, distributing “roles” among students, which helps to practice language intonation.

Speech skills are also good to practice in an intensive reading lesson. For example, a book usually has a colorful picture on the cover that relates to the story. Ask students to describe the picture and think about what it might mean for the content of the book. You can use the illustrations in the book (especially in low-level books) as comic strips and try to make up your own story based on them before reading the book. The Reading Method, also known as the New Method or the Reading Approach, was devised by Dr. Michael Philip West (1888-1973). During the 1920s, he was working as a Professor of English in India. Dr. West believed that everyone around the world should learn English. As English was an international language, he argued that it could make it easier for people from different countries to communicate with each other. He thought this would have a number of important advantages for people everywhere:

How did the Reading Method differ from other ways of teaching English?

At the time when Dr. West was working, the most popular method of teaching English to students in other countries was the Direct Method, also known as the Natural Method. This method focused heavily on spoken words, through students actively participating in class. They were encouraged to learn English words directly without translating them into their first language. Dr West thought this method was too time-consuming, as a lot of class time was taken up with the teacher talking, so each student didn't get much time to practise their speaking skills. He also believed that learning to read English was more important than learning to speak or write it - he thought the skills of speaking and writing English would naturally come later if students learned how to read it first.

This belief was at the very core of the Reading Method in English teaching, as the approach focuses on the "passive" work of reading, rather than the "active" work of actually speaking English. This is because Dr. West believed that you can't express yourself until you know enough words, and reading. The tasks in this learning phase focus on shaping students' reading comprehension skills such as identifying topic or main idea, supporting details, drawing inferences, and vocabulary in context. At the outset, teacher leads discussion facilitating the introduction of the vocabularies related to the topic of the passage. Next, the students will be given a passage to read within the group. They will be asked to pick 1 or 2 unfamiliar word(s) of each paragraph. They jot them down into the template made by the teacher. They need to justify the word class (noun, verb, adjective, or adverb), its phonetic symbol, meaning, and example how the word is used in a sentence. To help them do this, they can go to MacMillan Online Dictionary or Oxford Online Dictionary.

Picture -1. Reading strategies.

Reading Strategies

- **Pre-Reading-** gives you an idea of the contents of a selection, prepares you for careful reading later and helps you learn something about the author and his/her background.
- **Critical Reading-** reading for research purposes (reading the passage word for word). Critical reading is helpful when you need to make a decision on a controversial issue.
- **Skim Reading-** glancing through the entire page rather than skipping paragraphs; reading for details rather than main ideas.
- **Skip Reading** - reading only for the main ideas or for one particular purpose or concept.

This activity will be done in 15 Minutes. After that, I initiate the discussion of the text that aims at helping students respond to the text. Group discussion is implemented to engage students in collaborative reading tasks. They will be encouraged to analyze pros and cons points stated in the text. The following questions are used to help guide their analysis which they need to complete in 15 minutes.

Picture-2. Types of readers.

Active versus Passive Reading

Active Readers

- ◀ Skim headings to find out what an assignment is about before beginning to read.
- ◀ Make sure they understand what they are reading as they go along.
- ◀ Read with a pencil in hand, highlighting, jotting notes, and marking key vocabulary.
- ◀ Develop personalized strategies that are particularly effective.

Passive Readers

- ◀ Check the length of an assignment and then begin reading.
- ◀ Read until the assignment is completed.
- ◀ Simply read.
- ◀ Follow routine, standard methods.

What is the topic of the passage? What are the arguments for the topic of the passage? Write your reasons and evidence.

What are the arguments against the topic of the passage? Write your reasons and evidence. Students are required to draw the result of analysis into a poster/ mind map that depicts the answer of the questions. They present their poster to the other groups. When the students finish presenting the first reading task, I continue requesting them to engage in text analysis activity. It focuses on facilitating the development of students' understanding of the generic structure of the passage, communicative purposes of the author, and grammatical features of the text. With the same passage, the questions below are used to help guide their discussion in 15 minutes:

How is the text structured? Justify your answer.

What is the communicative purpose of the author writing the text?

What grammatical features are mainly used in the passage? Write some for evidence. Post reading tasks. In the final task, I design an activity that provides students with an opportunity to compose a piece of text or visual text. The goal of this task is to evaluate the students' understanding of the topic being discussion. They are required to write a paragraph of 100 words, or a poster based on their reading journey that predicts how the issue is going to be in the future. From this activity, I truly expect that the students can exercise their critical thinking with the knowledge they have internalized from reading the passage. Moreover, it gives students chance to express their ideas and thoughts responding to the issue. This task takes 20 minutes to do.

Reflection is an important part of learning because it allows students to see clearly what they have learned, how they do it, and what they can do next. To encourage reflective practice, students are given self-assessment tools to help them understand their own learning progress. The teacher's questions guide the students in reflecting on their learning. The questions should focus on the development of reflective practice skills and critical thinking. The students have 10 minutes to fill out the self-assessment table.

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